

Naturalista sicil., S. IV, XLVII (1), 2023, pp. 109-110

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8164828>

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HONEY BEE WATCH: AN INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC INITIATIVE FOR THE PROTECTION OF SURVIVOR COLONIES

Honey Bee Watch: un'iniziativa scientifica internazionale per la protezione delle colonie selvatiche

Honey bees are essential pollinators and the recent population losses that they are facing are threatening biodiversity and food security at large. Research aimed at solving these losses focuses mostly on searching for solutions by investigating conventionally managed and treated honey bee colonies. However, this context of investigation does not enable the study of honey bee traits in natural conditions and therefore limits the possibility for scientists of finding sustainable solutions to this alarming problem.

Honey Bee Watch aims to address this lapse by building an international coalition, developing digital scientific tools, and collecting data to better understand the biological, behavioural, and environmental traits that enable survivorship among free-living and untreated colonies around the world.

Honey Bee Watch has launched an online mapping platform, which will provide extensive data on the presence and localisation of untreated and naturally surviving honey bees. Once such colonies have been identified, implementations on the platform will be developed for enabling the monitoring of such colonies. Moreover, a network of regionally coordinated operators will be deployed to validate questionable cases and collect samples according to standardised protocols. Molecular tools and big data analyses will be utilised to assess colonies health and investigate their traits in relation to stressors.

As such, Honey Bee Watch will increase science capacity of mitigating

colony losses and will improve honey bee conservation and foster the protection of biodiversity.

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